

Ecosystem and Landuse Policy Group (ELPEG) Bulletin - May

Introduction

Welcome to this, our second ELPEG bulletin of the 2022-2027 RESAS strategic research programme. The aim of this bulletin is to provide policy makers with updates on the research on biodiversity that is happening within the strategic research programme. The bulletin will cover work from Topic D4 (Biodiversity) and the biodiversity elements within the air pollution Topic (D1).

For this bulletin we have updated the one-page summaries of the seven projects within the biodiversity topic and the one project within the air pollution topic that covers the impacts of pollution on biodiversity.

We welcome your feedback on this bulletin and if you have comments please do either provide them at the ELPEG meeting or contact Ruth.Mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

Contents

- [Introduction to Theme D and how to find out more about the work on Soils, Water and Natural Capital](#)
- [Nitrogen impacts in natural ecosystems](#)
- [Nature and People](#)
- [Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers](#)
- [Scotland's biodiversity: People, data and monitoring](#)
- [Habitat management and restoration](#)
- [Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future](#)
- [Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns, population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health](#)
- [Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands](#)

Introduction to Theme D and how to find out more about the work on Soils, Water and Natural Capital

Theme D - Natural Resources is one of five themes in the Strategic Research Programme. The others are A Plant and Animal Health, B Sustainable Food System and Supply, C Human impacts on the Environment and E Rural Futures.

Within Theme D there are five Topics D1 Air Quality, D2 Water (inc Flooding), D3 Soils, D4 Biodiversity, D5 Natural Capital. ELPEG and ELSEG will largely focus on D4 Biodiversity and the biodiversity work in D1 Air Quality.

Each Topic has their own mechanisms for engagement with policy and with stakeholders:

D1 – Air pollution

The project on ammonia emissions is working specifically with the CAFS2 (Cleaner Air for Scotland Strategy) Agriculture and Environment Working Group (AEWG) and the project on particulates with the CAFS2 Domestic Emissions Working Group (DEWG). The project on air pollution and biodiversity is engaging with ELPEG and ELSEG. Contact Andrea.Britton@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D2 - Water (inc Flooding)

This Topic has established an engagement group with SG policy (teams working on Water and Environment, Flooding, Water Industry team, Drinking Water Quality) and a wider engagement group (including NatureScot, SEPA, Councils, Scottish Water, NHS, land managers and communities). A summary of the projects in this Topic was circulated with the October 22 ELPEG bulletin called “RESAS Strategic Research Programme Topic D2 water - Summary of projects (June 2022)”. Work about one of the projects within this topic can be found at <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/achieving-multi-purpose-nature-based-solutions>. Contact Mark.Wilkinson@hutton.ac.uk for further details about work in any of the projects within the water topic.

D3 - Soils

The engagement will cover work in the Topic, Underpinning Capacity and other Topics in Theme D and with Themes A, B and C. It is envisaged that policy and public engagement will be delivered through the underpinning capacity (JHI-UNC-9) with other stakeholders engaged through the new ‘Soils Network’ developed in this topic. The Soils Network will include representatives of LEAF, Soil Association, Zero Waste Scotland, SAOS, NFU Scotland, AHDB. A copy of the latest newsletter produced by this Topic “The Soil Sentinel” is attached. Contact Eric.Paterson@hutton.ac.uk or Kenneth.Loades@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D5 - Natural Capital

A series of specific end user groups has been set up, one for each project in the topic. These involve, amongst others, SG, ONS, NatureScot, Defra, SEPA and the Office of the Chief Economic Advisor. A summary of the projects within this Topic was circulated with the October 22 ELPEG bulletin called “2022-27 D5 Natural Capital 6 x projects”.

Three things to highlight from the Natural Capital Topic that you may be interested in:

- (1) Mike Rivington has been developing his analytic approach - choosing what assets to represent etc - for a model to explore and represent how climate change affects nat cap. For anyone is interested

there are now several deliverables are now up on his webpage (<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/climate-change-impacts-natural-capital>).

- (2) The project on [Galvanising Change via Natural Capital](#) just has its latest newsletter out and available [here](#). Anyone very welcome to [subscribe by following this link](#).
- (3) Maria Nijink is a heavily involved in organising the 2024 IUFRO Congress (International Union of Forest Research Organizations) which will be in Stockholm. She is linked with sessions on social and institutional innovation and natural capital valuation and I understand she welcomes any interest in contributing or getting involved.

Please see the links below for details about the projects within the Natural Capital Topic:

- Bringing in Participatory Approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation (JHI-D5-1; Maria.Nijink@hutton.ac.uk): <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/bringing-participatory-approaches-widen-scope-natural-capital-valuation>
- Climate change impacts on Natural Capital (JHI-D5-2; Mike.Rivington@hutton.ac.uk) <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/climate-change-impacts-natural-capital>
- Galvanising Change via Natural Capital (JHI-D5-3; Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk) <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/galvanising-change-natural-capital>
- Modelling the socio-economic, greenhouse gas and natural capital impacts of land use policy and opportunities (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/modelling-the-socio-economic-greenhouse-gas-and-natural-capital-impacts-of-land%20use-policy-and-opportunities-2>
- Synthesis of natural capital and valuation outcomes Alistair (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/synthesis-of-natural-capital-and-valuation-outcomes>
- Understanding the value of Scotland's agricultural soil natural capital (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/understanding-the-value-of-scotland%E2%80%99s-agricultural-soil-natural-capital>

Contact Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk for further details about the Natural Capital Topic.

Nitrogen impacts in natural ecosystems

Lead PI: **Andrea Britton** (andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve understanding of the impacts of nitrogen deposition on Scottish natural ecosystems in the context of a changing climate, providing evidence on how natural ecosystems are changing, what is driving this change and how best to manage and protect them.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

- 1. Review of nitrogen and climate impacts on Scottish ecosystems** (Completed – see outputs)
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
- 2. Nitrogen and climate impacts on above and below ground biodiversity in alpine ecosystems**
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
Work has now commenced to revisit long term vegetation plots 50 years after the first sampling to examine how nitrogen and climate change are affecting plant and soil biodiversity in alpine habitats. Three hundred locations in mountain areas across Scotland will be visited over 3 years, at each location vegetation composition will be recorded and soil samples taken for soil chemical analysis and DNA analysis of soil biodiversity.
- 3. Nitrogen and climate impacts on woodland ectomycorrhizal communities**
Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk
Using data from the National Biodiversity Network and new data collected from birch, oak and pine forests across Scotland, we are investigating how nitrogen deposition and climate affect woodland fungal communities. Fungal communities were sampled by DNA sequencing at 15 semi-natural Scots Pine forests in the first year, covering a wide range of environmental conditions. Further sampling is planned for the current year.
- 4. Impacts of nitrogen climate interactions on ecosystem function**
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
Using long-term (20+ years) experimental plots in alpine heath we are investigating how warming and nitrogen additions affect carbon and nutrient stocks, nutrient cycling and above and belowground biodiversity. Sampling of vegetation and soils in the long-term plots was completed in the first year – in the current year these data will be used to calculate the effects of warming and nitrogen additions on the plant and soil carbon stocks and on soil biodiversity.
- 5. Modelling of nitrogen climate interactions**
Contact: mike.rivington@hutton.ac.uk
Starting in 2024, we will be using data gained from all studies to model risks to Scottish ecosystems from interactive impacts of nitrogen deposition and climate change.
- 6. Review of potential for mitigation of nitrogen impacts on Scottish ecosystems and metrics of success** (Completed – see outputs)
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
- 7. Experimental trial of nitrogen mitigation methods and indicators**
Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk
Starting 2023 we will trial a potential method for nitrogen impact mitigation in a Scottish ecosystem, with the experimental design guided by the review of mitigation methods.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Nitrogen and climate: a review of the interactive effects of nitrogen deposition and climate change on Scottish semi-natural vegetation.](#)
- [Nitrogen mitigation: a review of nitrogen deposition impacts and mitigation potential in Scottish semi-natural ecosystems.](#)
- Further information and project updates are now available from: www.hutton.ac.uk/NINE

People and Nature

Lead PI: **Katherine (Kate) Irvine** (kate.irvine@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Identify and evaluate interventions, approaches and processes to facilitate the transformative change of how Scotland's biodiversity is framed, valued, managed and governed, and how to harness and more equitably distributed the associated benefits.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

For further information on any of the objectives below please contact Kate.Irvine@hutton.ac.uk

1. **Nature and Economy:** Explore nature-economy relations and the implications of different framings for managing nature.

Completed literature review on nature-economy relationship discourse using the Life Framework of Values. This informed draft research protocol to inform Year 2 activity.

2. **Enabling inclusivity in biodiversity narratives:** Identify narrative and approaches which are usually outside of biodiversity research, and develop and evaluate audio-visual and interactive narrative tools and techniques to better enable their productive engagement for transformative change. Draft report.

Undertook review of policy, literature and existing relevant data, and conducted stakeholder interviews to identify marginalized biodiversity narratives. Evaluated spatial digital platforms/website technologies.

3. **Enabling transformative biodiversity research and change:** Examine how novel management interventions and transformative research can enable more diverse, sustainable and just futures.

Completed pilot interviews. Due to recruitment challenges, in consultation with RESAS we broadened the farm type beyond arable and expanded recruitment mechanisms.

4. **Values:** To understand the different societal, economic and biological values associated with biodiversity within nature conservation and farming practices, and how these values may be leveraged and changed with transformative research.

Conducted literature synthesis on Q-methodology assessing feasibility for assessing biodiversity values.

5. **Harnessing Green / Blue Infrastructure for people and nature:** Focuses on how to assess green-blue infrastructure for multiple benefits through investigating the impact of different types of interventions.

Completed interviews exploring impact of participation in nature-engagement programmes. Identified potential indicators for a quality of urban life survey to evaluate place-based interventions.

Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers

Lead PI: **Robin Pakeman** (robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to identify how the "IPBES drivers", specifically climate change, land use change, pollution and invasive species, affect key parts of Scotland's biodiversity.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Global change impacts on sustainable upland land use

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

Analysis of meadow pipit territory size and drone captured estimates of vegetation biomass indicate territories are smaller where spring biomass is highest and larger if autumn biomass is higher. Birds appear to need larger territories where there is a lot of purple moor grass which has leaves only in summer.

2. Collective landscape management of farmland biodiversity

Contact: graham.begg@hutton.ac.uk

A plan has been set up with a Farmer Cluster based in Aberdeenshire to support their adoption of appropriate biodiversity sensitive production practices. Monitoring strategies by scientists and citizen scientists have been agreed.

3. Using long-term aphid monitoring data to assess drivers of biodiversity change

Contact: ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk

Long-term aphid trap data has been collated alongside meteorological data from each trap location. Pesticide use and land use data are in the process of being requested. These datasets will be used to assess what is driving Scottish trends in aphid species abundance, composition and diversity.

4. Using Scotland's Caledonian forest as a model system to assess impacts of major climate drivers

Contact: alison.hester@hutton.ac.uk, jenni.sockan@hutton.ac.uk

Our "future drought scenarios" experiment on native Scots pine saplings is at an early stage but we have already picked up differences in resilience from immediate post-drought measurements. We are continuing to monitor bud burst and growth in this first year following drought treatments.

5. Assessing potential effect of chemical pollution on the wild Scottish salmon

Contact: zulin.zhang@hutton.ac.uk

Having selected typical Endocrine Disrupting Compounds (EDCs) we are developing analytical methods for monitoring these chemicals in water and salmon samples. At the same time, we are designing a sampling protocol for collecting water and salmon samples from River Dee.

6. Improved technology to track invasive non-native pathogens and their effects on ecosystems

Contact: david.cooke@hutton.ac.uk

Amplification of the new marker is working and matched sets of samples with the existing marker are being prepared for sequencing for cross validation. Both markers will be tested on woodland samples from the Cowal peninsula.

7. Impact Assessment of Invasive Non-Native Species

Contact: michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk; ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk Eleven new cost estimates were added to the international database of invasive species costs, including three plant species whose costs had not previously been included for Scotland. The UK National Vegetation Classification has been linked to the Defra Plant health risk register and the pests most likely to establish in the UK that can be hosted on plants occurring in natural habitats extracted. Five methods to identify which habitats to prioritise for surveillance of plant pests have been compared.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Pakeman, R. (2022) Grassland Ecology. Farm Wilder Grassland Ecology Webinar
- Roberts, M. & Li, K.H. (2023) Summary of UK and Scotland data in InvaCost database – Including updated Scottish data. Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12668570.v5>
- Mitchell, R. (2023) SEFARI case study: [Which habitats are at greatest risk from plant pests and pathogens?](#)
- Mitchell, R.J. (unpublished) [Comparison of methods to prioritise plant diseases and their hosts for surveillance](#)

Scotland's biodiversity: People, data and monitoring

Lead PI: **Jenni Stockan** (jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to help protect Scotland's share of global biodiversity by optimising people's skills, data, and technologies to ensure effective recording and monitoring techniques and data flows.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Creating a Scottish biodiversity inventory

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We are investigating how a more comprehensive and balanced inventory of Scottish biodiversity can be created. Working closely with the NBN, we are beginning to identify major knowledge gaps in our current inventory (e.g. cryptic soil biodiversity). We have begun case studies of functionally important groups to assess how distinctive our biodiversity is in a UK and global context.

2. Improved reporting

Contact: kit.macleod@hutton.ac.uk robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

Including information on distribution and abundance alters habitat level trend data for bryophytes and lichens, reducing mean occupancy but not affecting overall trends. We are in discussion with Better Biodiversity Data staff to explore infrastructure improvements that could enhance State of Nature reporting and biological recording data flows.

3. Genetic diversity of mountain hares and their capacity to adapt

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We have developed a non-invasive genetic sampling method to assess the use of genetic markers in the Scottish mountain hare. This method could provide the tools to quantify population size, genetic diversity, genetic mixing and introgression/hybridisation within difficult to survey species cost effectively.

4. Oceanic-alpine soil biodiversity

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

We are expanding our pilot citizen science project, which has already found fungi new to science, to collect soil samples from 270 Munros in Scotland to characterise alpine soil biodiversity. We are currently producing survey packs and outreach materials for a project launch at the end of May 2023, with sampling by volunteers planned to take place over summer 2023 and 2024.

5. Monitoring approaches for outcomes focussed interventions

Contact: cathy.hawes@hutton.ac.uk

As NatureScot's POBAS project draws to an end, we are continuing to work with them through development of a more generic Biodiversity Audit. The monitoring protocols developed thus far will now form the basis for an open access toolkit for farmers, guiding users through an iterative process of design, implementation and monitoring new management interventions to enhance on-farm biodiversity.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-highlands-islands-62150479>
- Partner in BIOSCAN project: improving DNA-based biomonitoring in the UK
- Article on indicators in *In Practice*, the membership publication of the Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management

Habitat management and restoration

Lead PI: **Andy Taylor** (andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To gain biodiversity in moorland and woodland habitats through evidence-based land management and restoration to maximise benefits to society.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1 How can public and private sector investors, at low risk, restore woodland habitats for the most multiple benefits to society in addition to increasing natural carbon capture and biodiversity, and what land is available for this?

Contact: matt.hare@hutton.ac.uk

Using an interdisciplinary approach that combines socio-economic data analysis, participatory community-based assessment and socio-biophysical modelling, this work is focused on reviewing and developing the evidence base on the flow of benefits to society and communities, as well as risks (related to climate change and investor behaviour) associated with restoring and expanding woodland habitats. This last year, among other things, we have been collecting interdisciplinary data and knowledge which has involved the development of a conceptual model of flows. Additionally, we have been carrying out a first spatial analysis and mapping of the vulnerability of native woodland expansion and corridors to climate change, as well as visiting examples of different types of native woodland expansion (e.g. through natural regeneration and new planting). This coming year we will be adding to this by mapping the flow of socio-economic benefits from such expansion; making a final selection of our two case study sites for the community assessment of benefits and risks (one rural and urban) and continuing the design and development of the integrated socio-biophysical model.

2 What is the impact of Muirburn on nature and how does this impact compare to mechanical removal of vegetation?

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

An investigation of the occurrence of wildfire in relation to the distribution and intensity of muirburn has shown lower likelihood of wildfire in muirburn areas. We have set up experiments at Glensaugh and RSPB Abernethy to assess and compare the effects of muirburn and mechanical cutting of heather on soil temperature, nutrient turnover and decomposition.

3 How do our ancient woodlands function and how successful is woodland restoration?

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We are assessing a) change in ecosystem services and properties when conifer plantations are established on ancient woodland sites, and b) how successful restoration is to restore these sites. Focus is on soil functional biodiversity. We have now identified six study sites representing a range from existing plantation, felled and recovering sites and old growth, oak woodland. We have established monitoring plots within these six habitats with seven replicates within each. Soil samples have been collected for edaphic biodiversity and soil characterisation. Nutrient probes have been used to assess soil nutrient levels and decomposition assays have been used to assess differences in ecosystem functioning.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Fieldwork and data collection has been completed.

Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future

Lead PI: **Ruth Mitchell** (ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve our understanding of how to design effective protected area networks against a backdrop of rapid environmental change and how to measure the success of protected areas.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Can applying a seascape approach to marine protection benefit biodiversity protection and improve fishery sustainability?

Contact: neil.burns@sruc.ac.uk

Our work develops on research conducted in 2022 – 2023 building on data collected from Loch Eriboll and Little Loch Broom. Last year's field season ('22) provided data to build seabed habitat maps (paper in review) from 332 Stereo Baited Remote Underwater Video (SBRUV) camera deployments. The camera deployments also collected data on fish abundances and field work in 2023 will continue this data collection. In combination these data will help build an understanding of the mosaic of habitats required to properly protect marine fish biodiversity. The project work will seek to establish which types and combinations of habitats are of particular importance for juvenile gadoids, wrasse, and coastal elasmobranchs.

2. How can protected areas ensure that threatened genetic diversity is safeguarded

Contact: jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk

For this work we are utilizing our Scot's Pine common garden experiment with pine trees grown from known mothers from 21 protected Caledonian forests in 3 replicated sites across different bioclimatic zones. We are analysing data from the early years of this experiment to quantify effects of nursery environment on seedlings from different populations.

3. Can we identify refugia for species which are unlikely to disperse quickly in the face of a changing climate

Contact: c.ellis@rbge.ac.uk

We deployed data loggers into three woodland NNRs. The dataloggers measured the climatic difference between sites, and within sites with respect to topography and stand structure, for summer 2022 and winter 2022/23. We are now analysing the microclimatic data to understand the potential of topography and stand structure for spatial planning, and their role in creating microrefugia that could protect dispersal-limited species under climate change.

4. How do we measure the success of our protected areas?

Contact: ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

We have collated data from two long-term vegetation data sets from 1970's-2000's to assess differences in vegetation change inside and outside protected areas, across a range of habitats within Scotland. In total there are 1775 plots and we have calculated changes in cover for a variety of species groups such as grasses, forbs and dwarf shrubs and changes in the number of species in these groups. We are currently analyzing whether there are differences in the scale of the change between plots inside and outside different types of protect areas.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: mother tree, cone and seed phenotypes, 2007.](#)
- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: field phenotypes, 2013-2020.](#)
- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: nursery phenotypes, 2007-2011.](#)
- Website: <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/protected-areas-to-tackle-biodiversity-loss-now-and-for-the-future>

Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns, population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health

Lead PI: **Eleanor Watson** (eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To investigate the microbial risks associated with rapidly expanded resident and migratory greylag goose populations on Orkney, and assess economic, conservation and social impacts.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Investigate transmission of *Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Campylobacter* and antimicrobial resistance between geese, calves and cattle and the wider environment

Contacts: clare.hamilton@moredun.ac.uk (*Cryptosporidium*), eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk (*Campylobacter*) and nuno.silva@moredun.ac.uk (antimicrobial resistance)

Goose faecal samples have been collected during the wintering season (November 2022) and goose, cattle and calf samples have been collected during pre-turnout of calves to pasture (April 2023) with further sampling planned during post-turnout in June. Samples have been processed to isolate *Campylobacter* and *Cryptosporidium* and archived for DNA extraction.

2. Development of molecular tools to genotype geese

Contact: keith.ballingall@moredun.ac.uk

Methods to extract goose DNA from faeces have been assessed and optimised using local faecal material and DNA of sufficient quality and quantity has successfully been extracted for molecular analysis. Methods to amplify loci of interest for goose genotyping have also been optimised.

3. Engage with stakeholder groups to inform project progression, assess impact of findings and highlight successful approaches for related studies

Contact: eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk and beth.wells@moredun.ac.uk

The project has been outlined to members of the Orkney Goose Management Group and summary documents have been prepared for wider circulation amongst stakeholders in Orkney to raise awareness of the project.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Project PI contributed to the recent publication [NatureScot Scientific Advisory Committee Sub-Group on Avian Influenza Report on the H5N1 outbreak in wild birds 2020-2023](#)
- Funding secured for collection and transport of goose faecal field samples from Icelandic greylag geese from the International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic

Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands

Lead PI: **Davy McCracken** (davy.mccracken@sruc.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Explore the relationship between carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to detect synergies and trade-offs and identify land management practices that optimise the benefits derived

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

Our work is focused on SRUC's Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms where we are focusing on carbon storage (in the soil, and vegetation), biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation.

1. **Ground-truth existing maps of carbon storage potential and flood mitigation using on the ground surveys and environmental sensors to monitor rainfall and water flow, and expand the spatial coverage of these maps to include all predominant habitats on the estate.**

Soil depth measurements trialed across a subset of lowland sampling sites and methodology adapted

2. **Supplement existing biodiversity datasets, through the collection of new biodiversity data to expand spatial coverage to cover all predominant habitats present on the farm, and implement innovative approaches to monitor biodiversity (e.g., acoustic sensors and camera traps)**

Audiomoth acoustic loggers deployed at the fourteen lowland sites for three days during August 2022, specifically focusing on bat detection. Pollinator transects carried out across all lowland (45 transects) and upland sites (36 transects) during July and August.

3. **Trial scorecards developed under NatureScot's project Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach (POBAS) in Scotland and the NatureScot Civtech Challenge Habitat Quality app to determine how effective proposed scorecards are as indicators of wider biodiversity**

Iceni-earth habitat score card app (for POBAS) tested at Kirkton. Report produced and sent to NatureScot

4. **Quantify the relationships between metrics relating to carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to identify synergies and trade-offs between these key ecosystem services, and identify land management practices that optimise these multiple benefits**

To complete in Year 4

5. **Utilise data from Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms to create spatial models of carbon storage, biodiversity conservation potential and flood mitigation for part of the upper River Tay catchment, and collect additional data to ground-truth these at several sites, to test the scalability of findings generated during this study**

To complete in Year 5

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [The use of sensors in this project is forming a case study for a separate Scottish Government funded Knowledge Transfer Innovation Fund project.](#)
- [A stakeholder engagement event \[involving colleagues from SEPA, NatureScot and Loch Lomond & The Trossachs National Park\] was held in May 2022](#)
- [The rationale behind the project formed the basis of an SRUC display at the Highland Show in June 2022](#)